

Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Part-XIV. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2,4-Bis(2'-aryl-5'-methyl/carboxymethyl-4'-thiazolidinon-3'-yl)-6-hydroxypyrimidine

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SEVERAL substituted 4-thiazolidinones have been found to have many physiological activities¹. It was of interest to incorporate these molecules into bioactive pyrimidine derivatives². In continuation of our work³, we have condensed 2,4-diamino-6-hydroxypyrimidine with different aryl aldehydes to yield the Schiff bases (2), which on treatment with thiolactic and thiomalic acids gave the substituted-4-thiazolidinones (3) (Scheme 1). The structures

R = Aryl
 3a; X = CH₃
 3b; X = CH₂COOH

Scheme 1

of the products have been characterised by ir, nmr and mass spectral study. The spectral characteristics are given for representative compounds with anisaldehyde (sl. no. 12, Table 1). The compounds have been screened for antimicrobial activity.

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity using cap-plate method⁴ at a concentration of 100 µg using gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* (4150) and *B. mageterium* (2087), gram-negative bacteria *E. coli* and *P. flourescens* (2141) and fungi as *C. albicans* (3100). Most of the compounds were found moderately active against different strains of bacteria and fungi. However, comparatively significant activity (zone of inhibition in mm) was observed in compounds bearing X = CH₃ and R = 2-thienyl (13-19), 2-nitrophenyl (13-16), 2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl (sl. nos. 13-15); and having X = CH₂COOH and R = 4-chlorophenyl (13-17), 4-hydroxyphenyl (13-17), 3,5-dimethoxyphenyl (13-22), 3-methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl (13-17), 3-chlorophenyl (13-19), 3,4-dichlorophenyl (13-19).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Shimadzu DR-1 435-IR spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a Jeol JMS D-300 spectrometer and nmr spectra on a Varian FT 80-A spectrometer respectively.

2,4-Bis-benzalamino-6-hydroxypyrimidine (2): Benzaldehyde (0.02 mol, 2.12 g) was refluxed with 2,4-diamino-6-hydroxypyrimidine (0.01 mol, 1.26 g) in methanol for 5-6 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol, (62%), m.p. 252° (Found: C, 71.33; H, 4.56; N, 18.49. C₁₈H₁₄N₄O calcd. for: C, 71.52; H, 4.64; N, 18.54%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400-3 200 (OH), 1 640 (C=N), 1 600 cm⁻¹ (ring skeletal); δ (DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₃) 7.0 and 7.80 (8H, 2d, 2 × ArH), 6.75 (2H, s, 2 × CH=N), 7.25 (1H, s, Py 5-H) and 11.2 (1H, s, OH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

2,4-Bis(2'-phenyl-5'-methyl-4'-thiazolidinon-3'-yl)-6-hydroxypyrimidine (3a; X = CH₃): Compound 2 (0.01 mol, 3.02 g) was condensed with thiolactic acid (0.02 mol, 2.12 g) for 8-10 h at 110-115°. The resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol, (59%), m.p. 220-2° (Found: C, 60.41; H, 4.18; N, 11.70. C₂₄H₂₀N₄O₃S₂ calcd. for: C, 60.50; H, 4.20; N, 11.76%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH), 1 700 (C=O) and 660 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); m/z 50, 53, 59 (base peak), 63, 65, 68, 71, 77, 82, 94, 98, 110, 120, 128, 136, 148, 150, 162, 169, 178, 182, 186, 204, 222, 238, 280, 282, 300, 338 and 536; δ (DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₃) 6.5-7.5 (8H, m, 2 × ArH), 3.75 (6H, s, 2 × OCH₃), 2.6-3.0 (2H, q, CHCH₃), 1.30 (6H, d, 2 × CHCH₃), 3.85 (2H, s, ArCH), 7.25 (1H, s, Py 5-H) and 10.05 (1H, s, OH).

NOTES

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	R	Schiff bases (2)		4-Thiazolidinones (3)			
		M.p. °C	Yield %	X=CH ₂ (3a)		X=CH ₂ COOH (3b)	
				M.p. °C	Yield %	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	Phenyl	252	62	220-2	59	>340	48
2.	2-Furyl	>340	65	>340	56	>340	43
3.	2-Chlorophenyl	258-60	71	278d	58	190	51
4.	3-Chlorophenyl	140-5	69	—	49	>340	47
5.	4-Chlorophenyl	284-5	66	242	53	228	48
6.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	>325	72	>340	60	262	45
7.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	295d	61	>340	44	>340	39
8.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	115-20	63	266d	49	>340	48
9.	2-Thienyl	265d	69	278d	60	>340	55
10.	2-Methoxyphenyl	227-30	60	266d	58	>340	52
11.	3-Methoxyphenyl	245	58.5	>340	57	>340	51
12.	4-Methoxyphenyl	240	73	205	63	182	53
13.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	290	68	>340	52	235	45
14.	2-Nitrophenyl	195	75	226	58	>340	47
15.	3-Nitrophenyl	140	78	242	56	>340	48
16.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	165	68	262	51	248-52	56
17.	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	123	62	212	57	174d	42
18.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	>320	32	340	41	>340	49
19.	Cinnamyl	190	69	260	59	238-42	44
20.	4-N-Dimethyl aminophenyl	62	59	155	53	>340	47
21.	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthyl	85	65	>340	50	>340	51
22.	9-Anthryl	90	71	171	69	>340	55

Similarly, other 4-thiazolidinones were prepared (Table 1).

2,4-Bis(2'-phenyl-5'-carboxymethyl-4'-thiazolidinon-3'-yl)-6-hydroxypyrimidine (3b; X=CH₂COOH): Compound 2 (0.01 mol, 3.02 g) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.02 mol, 3.00 g) at 160° for 2 h and then at 180° for further 30 min. The resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol-DMF, (48%), m.p. > 340° (Found : C, 57.40 ; H, 4.18 ; N, 10.68. C₂₈H₂₂N₄O₆S₂ calcd. for : C, 57.47 ; H, 4.21 ; N, 10.73%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 400-3 300 (OH), 1 310 (O=C-O), 1 710 (C=O) and 680 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C) ; m/z 44 (base peak), 50, 58, 64, 68, 77, 92, 96, 104, 120, 134, 150, 164, 175, 196, 225, 320, 337, 533 and 626.

Similarly, other 4-thiazolidinones were prepared (Table 1).

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